

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

Here is the April issue of J.UCS! Although this issue is quite small, I believe that the more applied researchers in our group will enjoy it. The next two issues are going to be substantial special issues on Knowledge Management representing the top papers of the I-KNOW '02 conference (see www.know-center.at/i-know02).

Here is a number of other exciting news:

(1) The editorial board keeps growing: more and more prominent computer scientists are joining up, making J.UCS by now quite a force in our area. This is also clear from the usage statistics, see next point.

(2) Usage of J.UCS keeps growing continuously and rapidly. Just to give you an idea that we are growing faster than 100% per year, here are the comparative figures of September 2001 vs. April 2002: Sites that visited J.UCS: September 4417, April 6414; Visits of users: September 7056, April 11818; Hits: September 170114, April 389848. Thus, papers in J.UCS are read by a large and fast growing community. Hence, it is well-worth to submit some of your best papers to J.UCS and also encourage colleagues to do so.

(3) Note further that all volumes of J.UCS (by now 7 years, 1995-2001) are also available in printed form, and so are some special issues. Do consult http://www.jucs.org/jucs_subscription/print.html for details. Why don't you encourage your library to order them?

(4) The special offer for a ten year subscription for J.UCS for a whole institution (universities at \$250.-, companies at \$500.-) for the years 1995-2004 is still good, see http://www.jucs.org/jucs_subscription.html for details. Please consider this special offer seriously, if your institution is not a J.UCS subscriber, yet. The great advantage of an institutional subscription is that no name/password mechanism is used, but access is granted based on IP numbers/domain names. If your library does not have the budget, how about using some project money for this. For ten years \$250.- seem like peanuts to me!

Enough for today, I am happy that J.UCS is growing as vigorously as it does. Let me also repeat: we welcome further submissions, and to handle them also further members with outstanding research qualifications for our editorial board. If you are interested in the latter, give me an E-mail shout!

Cordially,

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